

Study of the Physico Chemical Parameters of Mercuric Acetate*

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Manuscript received 20 January 1982, accepted 28 December 1982

Isoelectric point of mercuric acetate was determined by paper electrophoresis using (i) buffer solutions of acetic acid and sodium acetate (1 : 1) of different concentrations at fixed pH, (ii) solution of acetic acid and sodium hydroxide of different pH at fixed concentration, (iii) buffer solution of acetic acid and sodium acetate of same strength (0.1 M) in different proportions at different pH and (iv) sodium acetate solution of different pH, as carrier electrolyte. It is observed that the isoelectric point of mercuric acetate depends not only on pH but also on the concentration of carrier electrolyte.

ISOELECTRIC point of inorganic compounds has been studied by various workers¹⁻⁵. Kraus and Smith¹ used paper electrophoresis for demonstrating the change of charge on the chloromercurate complex with change of chloride concentration in the electrolyte. The isoelectric point of cadmium chloride was found by Lederer and Ward² to be in the region of 0.5 N HCl. Below this concentration Cd(II) travels as a cation and above this as an anion. Lederer³⁻⁴ also examined the movement of Fe(III) in thiocyanate solutions with various concentrations of alcohol. The movement of Po(IV) in dilute HCl solutions was also examined; Po travels as an anion in 0.1 N, 0.05 N and 0.025 N HCl. Recently Renko, Davorin and others determined the isoelectric points of some metal chelates electrophoretically.

These prompted us to study the behaviour of Hg(II) acetate in acetic acid and sodium acetate medium. It has been observed that mercuric acetate as migrant in acetic acid solution moves as cationic species whereas in sodium acetate solution as anionic species. Detail studies in this respect have been made using (1) buffer solution of acetic acid and sodium acetate (1 : 1) of different concentration at fixed pH, (2) solution of acetic acid and sodium hydroxide of different pH at fixed concentration, (3) buffer solution of acetic acid and sodium acetate of same strength (0.1 M) in different proportions at different pH and (4) sodium acetate solution of different pH, as carrier electrolytes.

Experimental

2% Solution of mercuric acetate as migrant and the carrier electrolytes mentioned below were used. A drop of the solution of migrant was taken at the middle point (marked) of Whatman No. 1 (1 cm × 34 cm) paper strip and current was passed for

definite period at definite voltage. The paper was then dried, developed with yellow ammonium sulphide and the distance of the spot migrated measured.

Results and Discussion

1. Carrier electrolyte : buffer solution (1 : 1) of acetic acid and sodium acetate of variable concentrations at fixed pH :

Current passed for 90 min at 220 volts. The results obtained are given in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that Hg(II) salt migrates towards the anode as an anionic complex when a mixture of 0.16 molar acetic acid and 0.16 molar sodium acetate in equal proportions is used as carrier electrolyte and Hg(II) salt migrates towards the cathode as a cationic complex when 0.14 molar acetic acid and 0.14 molar sodium acetate in equal proportions are used as carrier electrolyte. The cationic and anionic species formed would be possibly of the type $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})^+$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2^-/\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_4^{2-}$. There must therefore be an intermediate species which has no charge. The concentration of the electrolyte in which the species has no charge can be found out from the graph. The concentration corresponding to the isoelectric point of Hg(II) acetate will be in between these two concentrations of the electrolyte, when the pH is fixed (4.74) and is at 0.075 M as is evident from Fig. 1.

The isoelectric point in general is pH dependent. But the results in Table 1 indicate that the isoelectric point does not depend upon pH only, but may depend upon the concentration of the carrier electrolyte as well. So, it can be concluded that the isoelectric point of Hg(II) acetate can also be found out by varying the concentration of the carrier electrolyte i.e. concentration of buffer solution at constant pH 4.74.

* Presented at the 65th Session of Indian Science Congress.

TABLE 1

Carrier electrolyte (1 : 1)	Conc. of OAc ion	Movement of Hg(II) acetate mm	Mean movement mm	pH
(M)CH ₃ COOH + (M)CH ₃ COONa	0.5M	+5 to +17	+11	4.74
(0.5M)CH ₃ COOH + (0.5M)CH ₃ COONa	0.25M	+4 to +15	+9.5	4.74
(0.2M)CH ₃ COOH + (0.2M)CH ₃ COONa	0.1M	+4 to +13	+8.5	4.74
(0.16M)CH ₃ COOH + (0.16M)CH ₃ COONa	0.08M	+3 to +7	+5	4.74
(0.14M)CH ₃ COOH + (0.14M)CH ₃ COONa	0.07M	-3 to -7	-5	4.74
(0.12M)CH ₃ COOH + (0.12M)CH ₃ COONa	0.06M	-5 to -12	-8.5	4.74
(0.11M)CH ₃ COOH + (0.11M)CH ₃ COONa	0.055M	-5 to -15	-10	4.74

'+' indicates movement towards anode and '-' towards cathode.

Fig. 1. Isoelectric point of Hg²⁺ ion.

2. Carrier electrolyte : buffer solutions of acetic acid and sodium hydroxide of different pH at fixed concentration :

Current passed for 60 min at 220 volts. The observed data are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

pH of the carrier electrolyte	Movement of Hg(II) acetate mm	Mean movement mm	Isoelectric point from the graph
4.2	-5 to -13	-9	4.47 pH
4.25	-5 to -12	-8.5	
4.32	-3 to -12	-7.5	
4.45	-1 to -9	-5	
4.53	+2 to +9	+5.5	
4.60	+3 to +12	+7.5	
5.00	+4 to +14	+9	
5.05	+5 to +14	+9.5	
5.12	+7 to +15	+11	

'+' indicates movement towards anode and '-' towards cathode.

Table 2 shows that as the pH of the electrolyte increases, the migration of Hg(II) changes from cationic to anionic. In other words, Hg(II) acetate has a tendency to form anionic complex with the carrier electrolyte as the pH increases. It has also been observed from Table 2 that Hg(II) moves towards the cathode when the pH of the electrolyte is 4.45 whereas it moves towards the anode at pH

4.53 of the electrolyte. This indicates that the intermediate species, which has no charge, will form in between these two pH at fixed concentration of the carrier electrolyte.

A graph can be obtained by plotting pH of the electrolyte against migration of Hg(II) acetate (Fig. 2). The isoelectric point of Hg(II) acetate can be found out from Fig. 2 and is at pH 4.47.

Fig. 2. Isoelectric point of Hg²⁺ ion.

3. Carrier electrolyte : sodium acetate solutions of different pH varying from pH 7.80 to 8.96 :

Current passed for 15 min at 800 volts. The observed results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

pH of the carrier electrolyte	Movement of Hg(II) acetate mm	Mean movement mm	Isoelectric point from the graph
7.80	-3 to -11	-7	8.21 pH
7.99	-2 to -7	-4.5	
8.11	0 to -8	-4	
8.15	-2 to +4	+1	
8.17	0 to +6	+3	
8.79	+2 to +10	+6	
8.93	+5 to +13	+9	
8.96	+6 to +15	+10.5	

'+' indicates movement towards anode and '-' towards cathode.

TABLE 4

Carrier electrolyte	Movement of Hg(II) acetate mm	Mean movement mm	pH
100 ml (0.1M) CH ₃ CO ₂ H	-5 to -14	-9.5	2.82
90 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 10 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-5 to -13	-9	3.72
80 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 20 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-4 to -13	-8.5	4.05
70 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 30 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-3 to -11	-7	4.27
60 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 40 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-4 to -11	-7.5	4.45
50 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 50 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-3 to -12	-7.5	4.63
40 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 60 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-3 to -10	-6.5	4.80
30 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 70 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-2 to -10	-6	4.99
20 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 80 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-2 to -9	-5.5	5.23
10 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 90 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-2 to -6	-4	5.57
5 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 95 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-2 to -9	-5.5	6.00
2 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 98 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-2 to -8	-5	6.43
1 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ H + 99 ml CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	-1 to -6	-3.5	6.73
100 ml (0.1M) CH ₃ CO ₂ Na	+1 to +6	+3.5	8.79

'+' indicates movement towards anode and '-' towards cathode.

From these data the isoelectric point of Hg(II) acetate can be found out as shown in Fig. 3. The data show that both the cationic and anionic species are formed with the carrier electrolyte. At pH 8.15, Hg(II) moves as a cationic species and at pH 8.17 as an anionic species. So, the species which has no charge will be formed with the electrolyte of pH in between these two but is found to be at pH 8.21 from the graph.

Fig. 3. Isoelectric point of Hg²⁺ ion.

4. Carrier electrolyte : buffer solution of acetic acid (0.1 M) and sodium acetate (0.1 M) in different proportions and of different pH :

Current passed for 15 min at 800 volts. The results observed are given in Table 4.

Table 4 shows that Hg(II) ion migrates towards the cathode when the carrier electrolyte is 0.1 M acetic acid and it also migrates towards the cathode when the carrier electrolyte is a buffer solution of 0.1 M acetic acid and 0.1 M sodium acetate even in the proportion of 1 : 99 by volume. Hg(II) ion migrates towards the anode when the carrier electrolyte is 0.1 M sodium acetate.

It is also observed from Table 4 that the migration of Hg(II) changes from cationic to anionic

from pH 6.73 to pH 8.79. So, the isoelectric point of Hg(II) acetate will be in between these two pH.

A graph is obtained by plotting pH of the electrolytes against movement of Hg(II) (Fig. 4). The isoelectric point of Hg(II) acetate can be found out from the graph and is at pH 7.75.

Fig. 4. Isoelectric point of Hg²⁺ ion.

It can be established by the present work that the isoelectric point of an inorganic ion is not only pH dependent but is also dependent on the concentration of the carrier electrolyte. Alternatively, the isoelectric point can also be expressed as the concentration at which the molecule carries no charge.

Acknowledgement

The authors record their sincere thanks to Professor N. N. Ghosh, Department of Pure Chemistry, Calcutta University, for valuable suggestions.

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